

Uranium is a Low-Risk Multi-Bagger¹

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Summary

Uranium is a vital resource for the nuclear industry and for the energy mix of all industrialized nations;

Further to Fukushima's disaster a devastating bear market lasting eight years has driven the price to rock bottom levels leading to mines closures;

A basement has been made for three years where the smart money has been accumulating;

The upside potential is rather unconstrained as demand is rather insensitive to the price, given that Uranium just represents 3-5% of the operating costs of a nuclear facility;

Focus on anthropic CO₂ and pollution control mainly in India and [China](#) will end up promoting nuclear energy as no other source of clean, reliable and scalable energy capable of satisfying base loads of modern societies has yet been invented.

Uranium a Wonderful Metal Forever

Uranium is not an uncommon metal, being for example 40 times more frequent than silver and 500 times more than gold, and its primary geological setting varies depending on whether the ore-body is a primary source mainly located in granite and more specifically leuco-granite (depleted in [femic minerals](#) with [ore-formation implications](#)) or whether it is a secondary setting, where uranium has been moved as it is easily soluble in draining surface waters (changing its valence) and further concentrated through redox reactions in a sedimentary setting (uranium is mobile under oxidizing conditions and precipitates under reducing conditions, and thus the presence of a reducing environment is essential for the formation of uranium deposits).

Concentration in the various types of occurrences can be summarized in the following table as per the [World Nuclear Association](#) WNA.

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Very high-grade ore (Canada) – 20% U	200,000 ppm U
High-grade ore – 2% U	20,000 ppm U
Low-grade ore – 0.1% U	1000 ppm U
Very low-grade ore* (Namibia) – 0.01% U	100 ppm U
Granite	3-5 ppm U
Sedimentary rock	2-3 ppm U
Earth's continental crust (av)	2.8 ppm U
Seawater	0.003 ppm U

And the various types of uranium Deposits (IAEA Classification) can be found [here](#) and a more complete presentation “*Assessment of uranium deposit types and resources — a worldwide perspective*” is found in the Proceedings of a Technical Committee Meeting organized by the International Atomic Energy Agency and the OECD Nuclear Energy Agency and published by the IAEA [here](#) in Dec. 2001. Unconformity-type uranium deposits host high grades relative to other uranium deposits and include some of the largest and richest deposits known. They occur in close proximity to major unconformities between relatively quartz-rich sandstone comprising the basal portion of relatively un-deformed sedimentary basins and deformed metamorphic basement rocks. These sedimentary basins are typically of Proterozoic age, however some Phanerozoic examples exist. The two most significant areas for this style of deposit are currently the Athabasca Basin in Saskatchewan, Canada, and the McArthur Basin in the Northern Territory, Australia as presented [here](#).

From the standpoint of this article, even though uranium was found and exploited in many countries the supply side comes mainly from four countries, representing more than 73% of the 2014 worldwide production. Overall the 9 countries listed in the Table below account for 95% of the world supply, this situation leading all countries running a nuclear set of power facilities to hoard precautionary stocks (like oil) of in between 2,5 and 5 years of consumption and especially more so those having depleted their resources (e.g. France).

	2014 t/U	Delta 13-14	% World Prod.
1 Kazakhstan	23127	+2 %	41,14%
2 Canada	9134	-2 %	16,25%
3 Australia	5001	-21 %	8,90%
4 Niger	4057	-10 %	7,22%
5 Namibia	3255	-25 %	5,79%
6 Russia	2990	-5 %	5,32%
7 Uzbekistan	2400	0 %	4,27%
8 United-States	1919	+5 %	3,41%
9 China	1500	+3 %	2,67%
	53383		94,96%
All countries	56218		

Strategic stocks, the status of remaining undisclosed, will make the assessment of the demand / supply equilibrium more difficult as many other factors playing a role are also difficult to assess

(transformation and recycling of high-grade military U into low-grade (4-5% U_{235}) nuclear fuel, underfeeding or reprocessing of tails by enrichers, etc. all factors contributing to making a challenge for the investor wishing to evaluate whether the market is oversupplied, in equilibrium or under supplied.

One should notice that Uranium mined and used during the period 1945-2016 (i.e. 2,797 Mt) represents somehow 50% of the world known remaining uranium resources (i.e. 5,718 Mt), moreover at the current consumption rate of approximately 65000 t U / year (i.e. 76650 t U_3O_8) it would take 90 years or so to completely deplete the known resources. The various sources of uranium, including secondary sources (civil stockpiles increased in the wake of the Fukushima disaster) are presented [here](#). Uranium [production](#) stands at 92% of world demand and therefore secondary markets play a major role in setting the price on the uranium [market](#).

Uranium is also present in the water, especially seawater in a concentration of 3 mg/m³, i.e. a thousandth of what is found in rocks. But given the huge reservoir represented by the oceans, several techniques have been used to attempt its recovery by means of ion-exchange polymer absorbent strips. At more than ten times the current price (according to a US DOE-funded work, i.e. > 600\$/kg), seawater might become a potential source of unlimited amounts of uranium. Predictions of the future availability of uranium, which are based on current cost and price data, as well as current geological knowledge, are likely to prove extremely conservative and even though the 1945-2016 consumption represents somehow 50% of the world known remaining uranium resources as stated above, one might infer that uranium will remain forever a major source of fuel for base-load energy supply for mankind, especially as we make a more efficient usage of it.

Over the years 1980 to 2008 the electricity generated by nuclear power increased 3,6-fold while uranium used increased by a factor of only 2,5 as the efficiency of the reactors increased. With electricity demand by 2040 expected (by the OECD's International Energy Agency in its World Energy Outlook 2016 report) to increase 67% from that of 2014, there is plenty of scope for growth in nuclear capacity in a world concerned with limiting carbon emissions, this being a major card on the Bull case player.

Fukushima, a Milestone

In 2007, the price of uranium hit the 153\$/lbs (pounds, i.e. 0,45359237 kg) inflation adjusted mark and engaged in a bear market that lead it to slightly above the 40\$ at the end of the 2009 global financial crisis and then started to gently recover up to 80\$ when the March 11, 2011 earthquake and subsequent tsunami off the Pacific coastline of Japan's Tohoku region caused severe damage at the Tokyo Electric Power Company's Fukushima Nuclear Power Stations and particularly at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Station. Subsequently, power plants were shut down one by one, as each one underwent their scheduled periodic inspections and by May, 2012 all power stations had suspended operations. Further to the TEPCO's Fukushima Daiichi NPS accident the Reactor Regulation Act was drastically revised and the Nuclear Regulation Authority (NRA) was established on September 19,

2012. But Japan as of March 2011 made up about one-fifth of the world's uranium consumption and had 54 reactors running.

These events lead to a protracted and severe bear market and in a sense mirror the 1970-1995 cycle where the oil shock pushed uranium prices to 176\$/lbs inflation adjusted to see them collapse after Three Mile Island (1979) and Chernobyl (1986) to the 7,1\$/lbs in Dec. 2001. It took then just six years for a raging Bull market to bring them back to 153\$/lbs, more than 20 times its depressed price with much larger impact on the stock price of uranium miner as the impact on their margins delivers a greater leverage on profitability. The bottom of the late cycle was made on the 1st of Nov. 2016 at a spot price low of 18\$/lbs and the current price of 28\$/lbs is already 55% higher while the mining industry is still in the doldrums.

Undoubtedly, the timing of uranium price recovery will be a function of Japanese restarts as they accounted for 13% of world uranium demand before Fukushima and as Japanese utilities have resold on the secondary market the excess purchase that they have kept making due to long term contracts that they partially kept honoring. The secondary supply plays a major role as primary mine production supplies approximately 86% of current demand. The balance of demand is supplied from secondary sources such as commercial inventories, reprocessing of spent fuel, sales by uranium enrichers (underfeeding leading to sales of U₃O₈ or UF₆ or reprocessing of tails or other recycled supplies) and inventories held by governments, in particular, the U.S. Department of Energy. But most importantly, in the wake of the Fukushima disaster, approximately one-third of the secondary supply is now attributed to Japan shutdown.

Percentage Variation in Uranium Requirements and Energy Input to Enrichment with Different Tails Assay, from a Base of 0.22% U-235

Figure borrowed from [WNA](#).

In respect to underfeeding (or overfeeding), the enricher will base its decision on the plant economics together with uranium and energy prices. The World Nuclear Association's 2015 Nuclear Fuel Report estimates that by underfeeding, the enrichers have the potential to contribute 5700 to 8000tU/yr to world markets until 2025 on the basis of typical Western 0.22% tails assay. With reduced demand for enriched uranium following the Fukushima accident, enrichment plants have continued running, since it is costly to shut down and re-start centrifuges. The surplus SWU (Separative Work Units) output can be sold, or the plants can be underfed so that the enricher ends up with excess uranium for sale, or with enriched product for its own inventory and later sale. The inertia of the enrichment process thus exacerbates over-supply in the uranium market and depresses SWU prices (from \$160/SWU in 2010, the spot price in March 2016 was \$60). With forecast overcapacity, it is likely that some older cascades will be retired.

As illustrated by the above figure, if to produce one kilogram of uranium enriched to 5% U_{235} requires 7.9 SWU when the plant is operated at a tails assay 0,25%, it will require 8.9 SWU (14% more) if the tails assay is 0.20% (thereby requiring only 9.4 kg instead of 10.4 kg of natural U feed, the 14% more energy spent leaving the enricher with 1kg of U to be resold on the secondary market). There is always a trade-off between the cost of enrichment SWU and the cost of uranium. The enriched UF_6 is converted to UO_2 and made into fuel pellets – ultimately a sintered ceramic, which are encased in metal tubes to form fuel rods, typically up to four meters long. A number of fuel rods make up a fuel assembly, which is ready to be loaded into the nuclear reactor.

Secondary supplies, consisting largely of government inventories (hard to monitor), enricher underfeeding and tails re-enrichment, where the economics differ considerably from mined production, have been a significant contributor to the supply-demand imbalance in the market. In addition, supply from some producers, whose production decisions are not necessarily driven by the economics of the uranium market, such as large diversified miners where uranium is just one of the several metals exploited in multi-metals mines and companies mining uranium for strategic purposes, has been a contributor to the imbalance. Finally, unprofitable production at the spot price continues to be supported by higher prices under long-term contracts and/or advantageous foreign exchange rates.

By the end of 2017 and in 2018, we began to see evidence that, at today's low uranium prices, not only is some of the higher cost production at risk but even the lowest-cost production faces planned and unplanned risks and mines started [closing](#).

Looking ahead, UxC expects that secondary sources of supply will fall from 2016 levels of 45,9 million pounds U_3O_8 per year to only 30,7 million pounds U_3O_8 per year by 2025.

Nevertheless, one should notice that further to the Fukushima accident no nuclear plant was stopped either in the US or in Europe even after a careful re-assessment of the increased security measures arising in the wake of Fukushima (Fergusson and Jansson, 2013). Furthermore, the Obama administration has included nuclear energy along with other non-carbon emitting sources in its "Clean Energy Standard" (Makinson, 2011).

Nuclear energy remains promised a bright future to help mankind achieve development at an affordable cost, especially as base load electricity (available 24h/365d) remains the key to improving the living conditions of several billions of human on earth, power that is required to have healthcare, education, transportation and communications systems. The nuclear facilities also provide that energy reliably and affordably as nuclear reactors can run on a single load of fuel for about 12 – 18 months, helping to shield utilities from possible fuel cost swings and supply interruptions.

Upside Potential

Today there are some 450 nuclear power reactors operating in 30 countries. Nuclear power capacity worldwide is increasing steadily, with over 50 reactors under construction in 15 countries. Most reactors on order or planned are in the Asian region (while Germany has curiously planned the shutdown of its entire park due to the political pressure of the “Green” and going against the grain of common sense) and there are also major plans for new units in Russia and significant further capacity is being created by plant upgrading. A list of power reactors under construction, facilities for which increased capacity is sought (leading to an increase in uranium consumption) and lifetime extensions is available [here](#).

The upside potential for the price of uranium is rather unconstrained as demand is rather insensitive to the price, given that Uranium just represents 3-5% of the operating costs of a nuclear facility, and furthermore one should note that at the prices which utilities are likely to be paying for current delivery, only one-third of the cost of the fuel loaded into a nuclear reactor is the actual ex-mine (or other) supply. The balance is mostly the cost of enrichment and fuel fabrication, with a small element for uranium conversion.

Nobody knows how long the basement will take before starts a new raging Bull run, but the low at 18\$/lbs in 2016 corresponds somehow inflation adjusted and cost of capital incorporated (say 6,3%) at the price of 7,1\$/lbs in Dec. 2001, $=1,063^{15} \cdot 2,5 \cdot 7,1 = 17,75$ \$/lbs in 2016. By the way, [mines' closures](#) and a totally depressed industry in 2016-2018 compares to the atmosphere that prevailed to the Oren L. Benton's horribly wrong short that precipitated Nuexco in [bankruptcy](#) in 1995 as everybody could only see the price of uranium down (borrowing millions of lbs of U from utilities to sell them short expecting to repay them with cheap uranium imported from the former Soviet Union and Russia until a ban was enacted by the US administration for dumping). As history rimes, the U.S. administration opened an investigation this summer 2018 into whether uranium imports threaten national security, a move that may lead to tariffs on the fuel and lead to a massive breakout of Energy Fuels Inc. (UUUU) the week ending 6/25/2018. American producers want about 25 percent of the domestic market to be reserved for domestic miners, whose 2017 production was the lowest in at least 25 years. But the bottom may be forming as Cameco's president and CEO's Gitzel stated “We will not produce from our tier-one assets to deliver into an oversupplied spot market and until we are able to commit our production under long-term contracts that provide an acceptable rate of return for our owners, we do not plan to restart”. As Rick Rule's President and CEO, Sprott US Holdings Inc., says: “the lights are simply going off” and the price of uranium can only go up from here. It's now just a question of patience, curiously often one of the most seldom feature displayed by investors.

One thing to add is that 15 years ago, 90% of the uranium purchases were made by the utilities, whereas [financiers](#), [investors](#) and speculators represent more than 35% today of the purchases. The reason for having made this rather long introduction to the uranium market is to enable the reader to get a picture of how complex the supply side is and how the demand side is also getting more sophisticated than before. This should convince the reader that he should hardly believe anyone saying that he knows when this market will solve its imbalances, even though the bottom seems firmly in. In order for a Bull run to start, there must be a trigger and it might well be both the resumption of the Japanese nuclear plants and the renewal of long term contracts which are slowly coming to terms and for which no reliable provider, no serious mining company will commit itself without significantly higher prices that would ensure reasonable margins and financial security to the operations.

URA, CCJ, NXE, UEC & UUUU

There are various ways to get exposure to uranium even though getting direct exposure to the yellow cake U_3O_8 seems only possible via [YCA](#). One can either purchase securities of mining companies listed on public exchanges such as CCJ, NXE, UEC or UUUU, buy the ETF [URA](#) or invest on the [AIM](#) listed YCA.

As of mid-2018, the Global X Uranium ETF [URA](#) sought to provide investment results that corresponded generally to the price and yield performance, before fees and expenses, of the

Solactive Global Uranium Total Return Index (“Underlying Index”). During the second quarter of 2018, the Fund began to seek to track the Solactive Global Uranium & Nuclear Components Transition TR Index, which is an interim index that leads to gradually reduce exposure to small-capitalization stocks while proportionately increasing exposure to other stocks based on their weightings in the Solactive Global Uranium & Nuclear Components Total Return Index.

During the third quarter of 2018, the Fund has begun to seek to provide investment results that correspond generally to the price and yield performance, before fees and expenses, of the Solactive Global Uranium & Nuclear Components Total Return Index. This change is moving investors away from a somehow pure uranium play, though before the change only through mining companies, to a broader set of companies involved into the nuclear industry. One can read on the fund’s site “URA provides investors access to a broad range of companies involved in uranium mining and the production of nuclear components, including those in extraction, refining, exploration, or manufacturing of equipment for the uranium and nuclear industries”. This is a choice one should acknowledge before investing in URA, having its merits but also some drawbacks for “pure” uranium players.

As one can see from the “Yahoo Finance” chart displayed above, the fund URA has made a basement for 3 years now, with a low somewhere around 11,80\$. The breakdown at the top corresponds to the Fukushima disaster and various attempts to surge from the basement have been made without real success. Volumes have gotten extremely large in this accumulation phase and most of the participants in the downturn have probably been wiped out so far during the basement stage. Several news have triggered breakouts, such as the reduction from the output of mines belonging to [Kazatomprom](#) (01/2017), to the halting of mines belonging to [Cameco](#) (11/2017) but have all failed in starting a new Bull market. One should notice that over the same timespan the price of U_3O_8 has set a bottom at 18\$ on 11/1/2016 and has already moved up of kind of 50% as displayed on the following chart from Cameco’s [site](#):

Therefore we already have a significant divergence between the fund URA and the yellow cake itself. One might think that there is a logical shift in between the moment the underlying is turning North and the time when it will be visible in the companies' balance sheets and cash-flows after that margins be restored.

In fact, looking at CCJ's chart price above, one can observe a better match with U_3O_8 price as the low is made in 10/2016 simultaneously with the yellow cake and since then, even though Cameco had to undertake painful conservatory measures and cut completely its dividend, the stock is 44% higher than its through. The [ruling](#) in Cameco's favor in dispute with Canada's CRA has given a boost to the shares late Sept., but from a technical analysis standpoint, CCJ's chart is undoubtedly turning around and starting a "Bull" move. CCJ's fundamentals are undoubtedly the strongest with its reasonable debt and 630 million in cash and the company is a "sure" play for those wishing to be exposed to a renaissance of the yellow cake, with a levered free cash-flow of 1,84\$/share.

NXE, UEC and UUUU are much smaller companies than CCJ and represent much higher levels of risk for the investor. Energy fuels (UUUU) along with Ur-Energy Inc., have taken action by submitting in January a Section 232 [Petition](#) to the U.S. Department of Commerce to reduce the quantity of uranium coming into the U.S. from other countries and "[Bang for the Buck](#)" has noticed that the price chart displays a nice turnaround with a typical breakout as often portrayed in Stan Weinstein's [book](#). UUUU looks highly speculative as it would strongly benefit from a favorable decision of the US administration would U_3O_8 imports be curbed.

One could consider establishing a small and highly speculative position (<0,25% of your capital, in the range of 0,10-0,15% for large accounts) somewhere around the simple 200days moving average (MM200), i.e. 2,25\$. The risk/reward ratio looks favorable, keeping in mind that we deal with small companies.

Summing Up The Bull Case

One can summarize the “Bull” case in 10 points as follows:

Uranium has been in an 11-year bear market suffering at its worst an 85% decline from 2007 highs;

During the last bull market there were 24 reactors under construction, today there are more than 60 and Japan continues to restart idled nuclear plants;

No producer on the planet is covering production costs in the 20\$/lbs-30\$/lbs range and the industry average for all-in sustaining costs is around 50\$/lbs-60\$/lbs;

The price of uranium needs to go up to the cost of production or the lights will go out as Rick Rule says and producers can't continue with 40-30\$ loss per pound of uranium and reactors can't run out of fuel and won't stop, that's for sure. Long term contracts will have to be agreed at higher prices;

Even if some companies like GoviEx have some new projects in the starting blocks with exploration permits in [Niger](#) or in [Zambia](#), when the market turns, there will be no time for new production expansion as it takes 7–10 years to develop new mines. There is a scarcity of projects that are production ready due to the 11-year bear market in uranium and consequent underinvestment;

Demand would not be constrained even if prices of uranium skyrocket as the price of producing electricity from a nuclear reactor does not relate very much to the price of uranium. The uranium costs as a percentage of the cost of generated electricity in a nuclear plant are commonly between 3% and 5% of total costs;

Major uranium producer, like Kazatomprom and Cameco have curtailed production because of low uranium prices and oversupply twisting the supply / demand equilibrium;

Secondary supply has devastated the market and is now in decline. Japan is coming back online, enrichment underfeeding on the decline, DOE sales and other strategic government stockpile unloading reduced;

The number of uranium miners went from 500 to 40. Companies with capable management teams are probably down to 10;

Capitalization of all uranium producers combined is so small that even a small shift in money from the bubble tech stock sector and bond market can create exponential rise. Investors hate to wait in a basement but once the “Bull run” starts the sector is small and will now be pumped by utilities and financier alike.

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Disclosure: I am LONG URA.